

Spectrophotometric Studies on Complexes of Rhenium With 4-Phenyl Thiosemicarbazide

S. P. BAG and R. CHOPRA

Department of Chemistry, Jadavpur University, Calcutta-700032.

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The reagent, 4-Phenyl thiosemicarbazide reduces Re (VII) to Re (V) in concentrated sulphuric acid and forms a reddish-yellow complex with Re(V) having absorption maximum at 395 nm. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity for rhenium are $(9.1 \pm 0.09) \times 10^3$ and $0.0202 \mu\text{g}$ of Re per cm^2 respectively. The optimum concentration range is 4-16 ppm and the relative analysis error per 1 percent absolute photometric error is 2.70 percent. Spectral data show the formation of a 1:3 complex at 395 nm at 12.2 to 14.4 N H_2SO_4 medium. The stepwise stability constants are evaluated by extended Leden's and Rossotti-Rossotti's methods. The overall stability constant β_3 is found to be of the order of 10^8 .

RYASHENTSEY and Afanas'eva¹ reported the colour reaction of thiosemicarbazide with ReO_4^- in presence of Sn^{2+} ions in 3-5N HCl media. According to them, Re-thiosemicarbazide complex is not convenient for analytical work. The reactions of rhenium with substituted thiosemicarbazides were first studied by Geilman and Neeb². According to their report an intense colouration ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 510\text{nm}$) appears when 2, 4-diphenyl thiosemicarbazide is added to a warm (80°) solution of ReO_4^- in 6N HCl or 14-16N H_2SO_4 . Quantitative data for analytical determination of rhenium using semicarbazides are not available.

In this present work an attempt has been made to study the colour reaction of 4-phenyl thiosemicarbazide with ReO_4^- which is stable in 60:40 aqueous-ethanol in 13.6N H_2SO_4 . The ligand itself reduces Re(VII) and forms a reddish-yellow complex ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 395\text{nm}$) with Re(V). The metal forms a 1 : 3 metal to ligand complex, as determined by Job's and molar ratio methods. The presence of 1 : 3 complex is also evident from the values found for β_3 evaluated by Leden's and Rossotti-Rossotti's methods. The stepwise stability constants for rhenium complexes in solution have never been determined. The said constants for 1 : 3 metal-ligand system have hardly been determined by spectrophotometric method before. Leden's idea has been extended for evaluation of stepwise formation constants by graphical extrapolation using spectrophotometric data. The values agree fairly well with those obtained by Rossotti-Rossotti's method.

Experimental

Apparatus: All the standard measurements were done on the Hilger Uvspek spectrophotometer using matched glass absorption cells of 1.00 cm light path.

Standard solution and solvents: A stock solution was prepared by dissolving KReO_4 (A. R.) in double distilled water. Rhenium content of the solution were determined by Nitron's³ method. The ligand, 4-phenyl thiosemicarbazide was prepared by the method of Sen

and Gupta⁴. A freshly prepared 0.5%(w/v) ethanol solution of the reagent was prepared for present work. Pure ethanol was obtained by distillation of rectified spirit (90%) kept overnight over lime. The above distilled alcohol was again refluxed over magnesium for 6-7 hours followed by distillation.

Results and discussion

Absorption Spectrum: The absorption spectra of the complex at two different concentration of rhenium ($\text{Re} = 5.3706 \times 10^{-5} M$, Fig. 11 and $\text{Re} = 2.1482 \times 10^{-5} M$, Fig. 11) prepared in 60 : 40 aqueous-ethanol solvent media in presence of excess ligand were studied from 360-600 nm and were found to be reproducible. The acidity of the system was adjusted to 13-14.5N with cold concentrated H_2SO_4 . It has been observed that the complex shows maximum absorbance at 390-400 nm. As the reagent blank has negligible absorption at 395 nm, the absorbances were measured against 60 : 40 aqueous-ethanol as a solvent blank throughout the studies.

Fig. 1 Spectral curves of Re-thiosemicarbazide complex against solvent blank;
1A : $\text{Re} = 5.3706 \times 10^{-5} M$
1B : $\text{Re} = 2.1482 \times 10^{-5} M$
1C : Reagent blank against solvent blank.

Effect of acidity and effect of heating : The colour-intensity of the system was found to increase with increasing acidity. At lower concentrations of acid the reaction is slow. The absorbance of the complex is maximum and remains constant in the 8.5 ml–10.00 ml of concentrated H_2SO_4 in the final volume of 25 ml, i.e. 12.25M to 14.4N H_2SO_4 . It has been observed that the reaction is very slow at room temperature ($28^\circ \pm 2^\circ$) and it takes at least 4 hours for full colour development. The reaction is rapid when the solution is heated for 25 min at a temperature 89° – 90° , but heating above 100° destroys the colour. After the development of colour at 85° – 90° , the system was found to be stable at least for 6 hr in 13.6N H_2SO_4 .

Effect of Reagent : The effect of reagent concentration on colour intensity of rhenium complex at 13.68N H_2SO_4 was studied by varying amount of reagent solution. The absorbance was found to be constant from 3–8.0 ml of 0.5% reagent solution for 8 p.p.m. of Re.

Beer's Law : To study the linearity between the absorbance and the concentration of the metal ion, a series of solutions containing fixed amount of reagent and varying amounts of rhenium were prepared at 13.68N H_2SO_4 keeping 60:40 aqueous-ethanol solvent media and measured at 395 nm. It was observed that Beer's law is obeyed from 1–20 ppm of rhenium. The molar absorptivity and Sandell's sensitivity as calculated from Beer's law are $(9.1 \pm 0.09) \times 10^3$ and $0.020 \mu g$ of Re per Cm^2 respectively.

Composition of the Complex : The composition of the rhenium complex in 60:40 aqueous-ethanol solvent media was determined by the method of molar ratio which has been found to be reproducible at different ReO_4^- concentrations. Shows two curves at different ReO_4^- concentrations suggesting a metal-ligand ratio 1:3 in solution. The composition was further verified by Job's method of continuous variation.

Fig. 2 Molar-ratio plot

A : $M=R=4.296 \times 10^{-3} M$
 • B : $M=R=2.685 \times 10^{-3} M$
 metal taken in each case = 1ml.

Equimolar solution of metal ion and reagent were mixed in a complimentary proportions of 6 ml ($M=R=4.296 \times 10^{-3} M$) and 12 ml ($M=R=2.685 \times 10^{-3} M$). The experimental plot of absorbance measured at 395 nm indicated 1:3 interaction.

Oxidation state of Rhenium : The oxidation state of rhenium in the rhenium-thiosemicarbazide complex is +5, as the ligand reduces Re(VII) to Re(V) in concentrated acid medium. In another experiment rhenium was reduced with tin (II) sulphate in the presence of the ligand under similar conditions of acidity and the absorption spectra observed. The nature of the spectral curve was found to be exactly the same as obtained in the absence of Sn^{2+} ions, with absorption maximum at 395 nm and of similar intensity. The colour formation of the complex was found to be more rapid in presence of tin (II)-sulphate (5–7 min). This ensures that the ligand reduces rhenium (VII) to rhenium (V) forming complex with Re (V), where only the unoxidised form of the ligand compete for the metal ion. In this complex the ligand acts as a mono-valent¹⁰ bidentate chelating agent. Also it has been observed that when ligand is added after the reduction of ReO_4^- with tin (II) sulphate, lower results are obtained owing to the formation of some Re (IV) along Re (V). The ligand gives no colour reaction with Re^{4+} -sulphate prepared by standard procedure by reducing ReO_4^- with tin (II) sulphate in 8.8N H_2SO_4 medium⁵. Also there was no colour formation when the ligand solution was treated with K_2ReCl_6 under different conditions of acid and solvents. This eliminates the possibility of Re (IV) in the complex. It has been observed that when the complex solution prepared by the procedure for absorption studies is diluted with water to 0.1 to 0.2N H_2SO_4 , the black solid ($ReO_2 \cdot xH_2O$) separates due to hydrolysis. Thus it can be concluded that the ligand reduces Re (VII) to Re (V) and forms a stable complex which is only stable in high acidic medium and 60:40 aqueous-ethanol solvent system. That the coloured Re-complex is positively charged, was confirmed by ion exchange studies with a possible structure $ReL_3^{2+}SO_3^{2-}$.

Stepwise formation constants of Rhenium-4-phenyl thiosemicarbazide complex : The procedure for evaluation of the stepwise formation constants for 1:3 complex was examined by Leden's method⁶ and verified by the method of Rossotti-Rossotti⁷ which was originally applied by Lun⁸ and others.

Leden's method : To evaluate the stepwise formation constants, the following equilibrium is considered :

The function most commonly used is

$$\Psi_1(L) = \beta_1 + \beta_2 L + \beta_3 L^2$$

Since the reagent is used in large excess, it has been found that the free ligand calculated is nearly equal to the total ligand concentration. Thus during calculation $C_L = L$ is assumed.

At very low values of C_L , the first two complex, ML and ML^2 predominate and the function $\Psi_1(L)$ tends to a straight line of intercept β_1 and slope β_2 . When β_1 is known, the function

$$\Psi_2(L) = \frac{\Psi_1 - \beta_1}{L} = \beta_2 + \beta_3 L$$

was calculated to obtain the value of β_2 as the intercept of the plot of $\Psi_2(L)$ against L , and the value of β_3 as the slope of the line. Similarly β_3 was further checked by plotting the function

$$\Psi_3(L) = \frac{\Psi_2 - \beta_2}{L}$$

against L . (Fig. 3) The value of β_1 , β_2 and β_3 are given below :

$$\beta_1 = 7.6 \times 10^2, \beta_2 = 4.3 \times 10^5, \beta_3 = 3.2 \times 10^8$$

$$k_1 = 7.6 \times 10^2, k_2 = 5.6 \times 10^3 \text{ and } k_3 = 7.44 \times 10^2.$$

Fig. 3 Subsidiary functions Ψ_1 , Ψ_2 and Ψ_3 as functions of free ligand concentration.

Rossotti-Rossotti's method :

Since absorptiometric data are described by $2N + 2$ independent parameters, interpretations are extremely difficult for systems in which $N=3$ or more. Also the absorbance of a complex depends upon the total concentrations of ligand and central group.

For evaluation of formation constants, a common approach was made by assuming that only the first complex exists in solutions of very low free ligand concentrations and by determining the values of ϵ_0 , ϵ_1 , and β_1 from measurements in this region. When only first complex is present, we have

$$\frac{\epsilon - \epsilon_0}{L} = -\beta_1(\epsilon + \epsilon_1)$$

where ϵ , ϵ_0 , ϵ_1 , β_1 have their usual significance. Thus to evaluate β_1 and ϵ_1 the function $(\epsilon - \epsilon_0)/L$ was plotted against ϵ which gave a straight line of slope $-\beta_1$ and intercept of ϵ_1/β_1 (Fig. 4). The values of ϵ_1 and β_1 thus obtained were substituted in the following function :

$$\frac{(\epsilon_0 - \epsilon)}{\epsilon L^2} + \frac{(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon)\beta_1}{\epsilon L} = \beta_2 - \frac{\epsilon_2\beta_2}{\epsilon}$$

for solutions of slightly higher ligand concentration and it was solved graphically for β_2 and ϵ_2 by plotting the left hand side against ϵ^{-1} to give a straight line of slope $-\epsilon_2/\beta_2$ and intercept β_2 . To evaluate β_3 and ϵ_3 , values of ϵ_1 , ϵ_2 , β_1 and β_2 were further substituted in the following equation :

Fig. 4 Plot for ϵ_1 and β_1 obtained from Rossotti's method.

TABLE I—RHENIUM-4-PHENYL THIOSEMICARBAZIDE $M=R=2.6852 \times 10^{-3}$; ACIDITY = 13.68N H_2SO_4 TOTAL METAL CONCENTRATION = 10.740×10^{-5} WAVELENGTH = 395NM

Absorbance	Total ligand Conc., M/Lit. ($L \times 10^5$)	$\epsilon = \frac{A}{CM}$ ($\times 10^3$)	$\frac{\epsilon - \epsilon_0}{L}$ ($\times 10^6$)	$\frac{(\epsilon_0 - \epsilon)}{\epsilon L} + \frac{(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon)\beta_1}{\epsilon L}$ ($\times 10^7$)	$\frac{(\epsilon_0 - \epsilon)}{\epsilon L^2} + \frac{(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon)\beta_1}{\epsilon L} + \frac{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon)\beta_2}{\epsilon L}$ ($\times 10^{10}$)
0.040	5.370	0.3725	9.217		
0.078	10.740	0.7263	8.913		
0.117	16.110	1.089	8.937		
0.152	21.480	1.416	8.620		
0.188	26.850	1.751	8.504	-0.008	
0.224	32.220	2.085	8.412	-0.019	
0.250	37.590	2.328	7.997	0.033	-0.6580
0.288	42.960	2.681	8.054	0.006	-0.0932
0.295	48.330	2.747	7.131	0.0847	0.1087
0.310	53.700	2.887		0.1050	0.1005
0.323	64.440	3.007		0.1433	0.1253
0.337	75.180	3.137		0.1470	0.0885
0.351	85.920	3.268		0.1400	0.0487
0.366	96.660	3.408		0.1284	0.0136
0.388	107.400	3.538		0.1176	0.0114

$$\frac{(\epsilon_0 - \epsilon)}{\epsilon L^3} + \frac{(\epsilon_1 - \epsilon)\beta_1}{\epsilon L^2} + \frac{(\epsilon_2 - \epsilon)\beta_2}{\epsilon L} = \beta_3 - \frac{\epsilon_3 \beta_3}{\epsilon}$$

for solutions of excess ligand concentration. The plot of left hand side against ϵ^{-1} gave values of ϵ_3 and β_3 . The results are given in Table 1. The values obtained by this method are given below :

$$\epsilon_1 = 20.830 \times 10^3 ; \epsilon_2 = 2.47 \times 10^3 ; \epsilon_3 = 1.231 \times 10^3$$

and $\beta_1 = 4.44 \times 10^2 ; \beta_2 = 42.5 \times 10^5 ; \beta_3 = 29.0 \times 10^8$
 $k_1 = 4.44 \times 10^2 ; k_2 = 9.57 \times 10^9 ; k_3 = 6.8 \times 10^2$

The values for k_1 and k_3 by Leden's method agree fairly well with those obtained by Rossotti and Rossotti's method. But the value of k_2 by the latter method is slightly higher than k_2 by Leden's method. This higher value is probably due to some overlapping of other constants. However, the values indicate that the ligand molecules combine with the metal ion almost simultaneously.

Determination of metal to ligand ratio of 1 ; 3 and a positive value obtained for β_3 give clear evidence for the existence of the complex, ML_3 in solution. Thus it can be concluded from the above observations that 4-

phenyl thiosemicarbazid reduces Re (VII) to Re (V) with a possible structure $(ReL_3)^{2+} So_4^{2-}$.

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